

In Vitro Mucolytic Activity of Infusion of Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) Bulb

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Abstract

This study investigates the mucolytic activity of garlic bulb (*Allium sativum* L.) infusion on cow's intestine mucus in vitro. The garlic infusion was prepared using aquadest and tested at concentrations of 1%, 2.5%, and 6.25%, with 1% acetylcysteine serving as the positive control. The mucolytic activity was measured by the decrease in mucus viscosity using a Brookfield viscometer. The data were analyzed using ANOVA, followed by LSD tests at a 95% confidence level. The results demonstrated a significant decrease in viscosity at concentrations of 53.33 Cps, 80 Cps, and 126.67 Cps, compared to the control. The most effective mucolytic activity was observed at 6.25%.

Introduction

Mucolytic agents are commonly used to reduce the viscosity of mucus, making it easier to expel from the respiratory system. Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) has been traditionally used for respiratory relief. This study evaluates the *in vitro* mucolytic activity of garlic infusion on cow's intestine mucus, modeling respiratory mucus.

Materials and Methods

Fresh garlic bulbs were collected, and an infusion was prepared at 1%, 2.5%, and 6.25% concentrations. Cow's intestine mucus was used as a model, and the viscosity was measured with a Brookfield viscometer before and after treatment. Acetylcysteine 1% was the positive control.

Results

Garlic bulb infusion at 6.25% resulted in the greatest reduction in mucus viscosity, confirming its potential mucolytic effects. ANOVA analysis indicated a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between control and treatment groups.

Conclusion

Garlic bulb infusion exhibits effective mucolytic activity, especially at higher concentrations (6.25%). This supports garlic's traditional use in treating respiratory conditions.

Keywords

Garlic, Mucolytic, Viscosity, *In vitro*, Respiratory Health, *Allium sativum* L.

References

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